

Research Article

Formulation and Evaluation of Mefenamic Acid Emulgel for Topical Delivery

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Background: Approximately 74% of drugs are administered orally; however, they often fail to achieve optimal therapeutic efficacy. To overcome these limitations, transdermal drug delivery systems have been developed. In such topical systems, adhesive properties and formulation consistency are critical for ensuring safety, efficacy, and product quality. Although conventional dosage forms such as creams, ointments, and lotions are widely used, emulgels have emerged as a promising alternative. By combining the properties of emulsions and gels, emulgels provide a dual-controlled release system that enhances the delivery of hydrophobic drugs into systemic circulation through the skin.

Objective: The present study aimed to develop a Mefenamic acid emulgel to enhance drug penetration for the effective management of inflammation and pain. **Methodology:** Mefenamic acid emulgels were formulated using hydrophilic polymers, sodium alginate and sodium carboxymethyl cellulose, at concentrations of 1%, 1.5%, and 2%. Mentha oil was incorporated as a penetration enhancer. The formulations were evaluated for pH, physicochemical properties, solubility, drug content, and Fourier Transform Infrared (FTIR) analysis. Further performance evaluation included in-vitro diffusion studies and in-vivo anti-inflammatory and analgesic assessments. **Results:** The prepared oil-in-water (o/w) emulgels exhibited excellent homogeneity, superior spreadability, absence of grittiness, and were easily washable with water. FTIR analysis of the optimized formulation (F3, containing 2% sodium alginate) confirmed the absence of any drug-polymer interaction. The drug content across all batches ranged from 87% to 97%, with low standard deviation values indicating uniform drug distribution. In in-vitro studies, formulation F3 showed the highest drug release (99.528%) over 360 minutes, followed by F2 (96.849%). Release kinetics demonstrated a high correlation coefficient, suggesting a non-Fickian diffusion mechanism.

Keywords: Mefenamic acid, Emulgel, Sodium alginate, Sodium carboxymethyl cellulose.

INTRODUCTION

Topical drug delivery systems have gained considerable attention in the pharmaceutical field as effective alternatives to conventional oral administration. Although oral delivery remains the most widely used route, it is often limited by factors such as first-pass metabolism, gastrointestinal irritation, and reduced bioavailability, particularly for hydrophobic drugs¹. In contrast, transdermal and topical delivery systems bypass these limitations by providing a non-invasive, site-specific approach that enhances patient compliance and maintains relatively steady plasma drug concentrations². Among the various topical dosage forms, emulgels have emerged

as promising and superior dermatological formulations. Conventional topical preparations such as creams, ointments, and lotions exhibit certain drawbacks. For instance, lotions often possess low viscosity and reduced residence time on the skin, while ointments tend to be greasy and cosmetically less acceptable.³ Emulgels overcome these limitations by combining the advantages of both emulsions and gels. This dual-controlled system facilitates the incorporation of hydrophobic drugs into an oil-in-water (o/w) emulsion, which is subsequently gelled using appropriate polymers. As a result, emulgels exhibit improved stability, enhanced spreadability, a pleasant cooling effect, and better skin penetration⁴. Mefenamic acid, a potent non-steroidal

anti-inflammatory drug (NSAID) belonging to the fenamate class, is widely used for its analgesic and anti-inflammatory effects. However, oral administration of mefenamic acid is frequently associated with gastrointestinal side effects, including gastric irritation, abdominal pain, and peptic ulceration⁵. Additionally, its poor aqueous solubility poses challenges for effective permeation through the skin when formulated in conventional gel systems⁶. Therefore, the present study focuses on the development of a Mefenamic acid emulgel to enhance its topical permeability and therapeutic efficacy. Hydrophilic polymers such as sodium alginate and sodium carboxymethyl cellulose were employed as gelling agents, while mentha oil was incorporated as a natural permeation enhancer. This approach aims to develop a stable, effective, and patient-friendly topical formulation for the management of localized pain and inflammation⁷.

METHODOLOGY

Preformulation Studies

Preformulation studies are essential for evaluating the physicochemical properties of a drug prior to formulation development. These studies help in determining the suitability of the drug for dosage form design and ensure product stability and efficacy⁸.

I. Determination of Melting Point

The melting point of pure Mefenamic acid was determined using the capillary method with a Thiele's tube apparatus. A small quantity of the drug was filled into a sealed capillary tube and placed in the apparatus containing liquid paraffin. The temperature was gradually increased, and the point at which the drug completely melted was recorded. The melting point serves as an indicator of purity; a sharp and narrow melting range confirms the absence of impurities. The experiment was performed in triplicate, and the average value was reported to ensure accuracy and reproducibility⁹.

II. Identification of Drug (λ_{\max} Determination)

The identification of Mefenamic acid was carried out using UV-visible spectrophotometry by determining its maximum absorption wavelength (λ_{\max}).

Standard solutions of 10 $\mu\text{g/mL}$ and 20 $\mu\text{g/mL}$ were prepared in distilled water and phosphate buffer (pH 7.4). These solutions were scanned over the UV range of 200–400 nm, and the λ_{\max} was observed in the range of 280–285 nm. The analysis was performed against a suitable blank, and the obtained λ_{\max} value confirmed the identity and purity of the drug. This method is widely used for qualitative and quantitative drug analysis due to its sensitivity and accuracy¹⁰.

III. Solubility Studies

Solubility studies were conducted to determine the solubility profile of Mefenamic acid in different solvents, including distilled water, ethanol, and sodium lauryl sulphate (SLS) solution. An excess amount of the drug was added to each solvent to prepare saturated solutions, which were then subjected to intermittent shaking for 24 hours at room temperature to achieve equilibrium. The solutions were subsequently filtered, and the drug concentration was analysed using a UV spectrophotometer at 285 nm. The results were recorded as the mean of three determinations. These studies are crucial for selecting suitable solvents and excipients for formulation development, especially for poorly water-soluble drugs¹¹.

Preparation of Mefenamic Acid Emulgel

The emulgel formulations were prepared using both natural and semi-synthetic hydrophilic polymers, namely sodium alginate and sodium carboxymethyl cellulose (NaCMC), at varying concentrations (1%, 1.5%, and 2% w/v), to evaluate their effect on formulation properties.

Preparation of Gel Base

Accurately weighed quantities of sodium alginate and Sodium carboxymethyl cellulose were dispersed in purified water and allowed to hydrate under continuous stirring using a mechanical stirrer. The pH of the gel base was adjusted to 6.0–6.5 using triethanolamine (TEA), ensuring compatibility with skin pH and enhancing formulation stability. Proper hydration of polymers is essential to achieve the desired viscosity and consistency of the gel base¹².

Incorporation of Drug

Mefenamic acid (1 g) was dissolved in 95% ethanol to enhance its solubility and ensure uniform distribution within the formulation. The drug solution was then gradually incorporated into the prepared gel base with continuous stirring to obtain a homogeneous mixture. The final weight of the formulation was adjusted to 50 g using purified water¹³.

Preparation of Emulsion

The emulsion phase was prepared separately and remained constant across all formulations. The oil phase, consisting of mentha oil (acting as a penetration enhancer), Span 80 (lipophilic surfactant), and light liquid paraffin, was heated to 70–80°C. Simultaneously, the aqueous phase containing Tween 80 (hydrophilic surfactant), propyl paraben (preservative), propylene glycol (humectant and co-solvent), and water was heated to the same temperature. The oil phase was then slowly added to the aqueous phase under continuous mechanical stirring to form a stable oil-in-water (o/w) emulsion. Maintaining equal temperatures of both phases is critical to prevent phase separation and ensure uniform emulsion formation¹⁴.

Formation of Emulgel

The prepared emulsion was gradually incorporated into the gel base with continuous stirring until a uniform emulgel was obtained. The final formulation was allowed to cool to room temperature, resulting in a stable, homogeneous emulgel with improved spreadability and drug release characteristics. The combination of emulsion and gel systems enhances the delivery of hydrophobic drugs by improving solubilization and penetration through the skin¹⁵.

Evaluation of Mefenamic Acid Emulgel

The prepared Mefenamic acid emulgel formulations were evaluated for various physicochemical, in-vitro, and in-vivo parameters to ensure their quality, efficacy, and stability.

1. Physical Evaluation

All formulations were visually inspected for colour, homogeneity, consistency, occlusiveness,

washability, phase separation, and odour. These parameters are important indicators of patient acceptability and formulation stability^{16,17}.

2. Determination of pH

The pH of the formulations was determined by dispersing 1% w/v of the emulgel in distilled water. The pH was measured using a calibrated digital pH meter. Maintaining pH within the physiological skin range (approximately 5.5–7.0) is essential to avoid skin irritation and ensure compatibility¹⁸.

3. Spreadability

Spreadability of the emulgel was evaluated using a parallel plate method. Approximately 0.1 g of the formulation was placed between two glass slides (marked with 5 mm divisions) and allowed to spread under a specified weight for 5 minutes. The diameter of the spread circle was measured in centimetres. The test was performed in triplicate, and the mean value was reported.

Spreadability was calculated using the formula:

$$S = \frac{M \times L}{T}$$

Where:

- S = Spreadability
- M = Weight tied to the upper slide
- L = Length of the glass slide
- T = Time required to separate the slides

Good spreadability indicates ease of application and uniform distribution of the formulation over the skin surface¹⁹.

4. Homogeneity and Grittiness

The prepared emulgels were evaluated for homogeneity by visual inspection after setting in the container. A small quantity of gel was also rubbed on the back of the hand to assess uniformity and detect the presence of any aggregates or grittiness. A homogeneous formulation without particulate matter indicates proper mixing and stability²⁰.

5. Phase Separation

Phase separation studies were conducted to evaluate the stability of the emulsion system. Oil-in-water (o/w) emulsions were diluted with water, whereas water-in-oil (w/o) emulsions were diluted with oil to confirm the type of emulsion and check for any instability or separation. The absence of phase separation indicates good formulation stability²¹.

6. Drug Content Determination

An accurately weighed quantity (100 mg) of emulgel was dissolved in 100 mL of phosphate buffer (pH 7.4) in a volumetric flask. The solution was shaken for 2 hours using a mechanical shaker to ensure complete drug extraction. The solution was then filtered, and the absorbance was measured at 285 nm using a UV spectrophotometer, with phosphate buffer as the blank.

Drug content was calculated using the formula:

$$\text{Drug content} = \frac{\text{Absorbance} \times \text{Dilution factor}}{\text{Slope} \times 1000}$$

Uniform drug content ensures consistent therapeutic efficacy of the formulation²².

7. Permeability Coefficient (K_p)

The permeability coefficient was calculated to evaluate the drug permeation through the membrane using the following equation:

$$K_p = \frac{J_{ss}}{C_v}$$

Where:

- K_p = Permeability coefficient
- J_{ss} = Steady-state flux
- C_v = Total drug concentration in the donor compartment

This parameter reflects the efficiency of drug permeation across the membrane²³.

8. Fourier Transform Infrared (FTIR) Studies

FTIR analysis was performed to detect any potential drug-polymer interactions. Samples of pure drug, polymers, and optimized formulation were prepared

using the KBr pellet method. The spectra were recorded over a range of 4000–400 cm⁻¹ using an FTIR spectrophotometer (Shimadzu 8300, Japan). The obtained spectra were analysed for characteristic peaks and possible interactions²⁴.

9. In-vitro Drug Release Studies

In-vitro drug release studies were performed using a membrane diffusion method. The formulation was applied onto a suitable membrane, which was mounted on a test tube and suspended in a beaker containing phosphate buffer (pH 7.4) as the diffusion medium. The temperature was maintained at 37 ± 0.5°C, and the system was continuously stirred using a magnetic stirrer. At predetermined time intervals, 2 mL samples were withdrawn and replaced with an equal volume of fresh buffer. The samples were analyzed spectrophotometrically at 285 nm, and the cumulative percentage drug release was calculated²⁵.

10. In-vivo Anti-inflammatory Activity

Anti-inflammatory activity was evaluated using the carrageenan-induced paw edema model in albino rats. Edema was induced by sub plantar injection of 1% w/v carrageenan into the left hind paw.

Experimental Groups:

- Group I (Control): Carrageenan only
- Group II (Standard): Diclofenac gel + carrageenan
- Group III (Test): Formulation F3 + carrageenan

The formulations were applied 30 minutes prior to carrageenan injection. Paw volume was measured at 30, 60, 90, and 120 minutes using a plethysmometer.

Percentage inhibition of edema was calculated as:

$$\% \text{ Inhibition} = \frac{V_c - V_t}{V_c} \times 100$$

Where:

- V_c = Paw volume of control group
- V_t = Paw volume of treated group

This method is widely used for evaluating anti-inflammatory activity of topical formulations²⁶.

11. In-vivo Analgesic Activity

Analgesic activity was evaluated using the hot plate method. The latency time (time taken by the animal to respond to thermal stimulus) was recorded.

Experimental Groups:

- Group I (Control): No treatment
- Group II (Standard): Diclofenac gel
- Group III (Test): Formulation F3

An increase in latency time indicates analgesic activity of the formulation²⁷.

12. Skin Irritation Study

Skin irritation studies were conducted using albino rats. The animals were maintained under standard laboratory conditions with free access to food and water. The dorsal surface of the rats was shaved, and an area of approximately 4 cm² was marked. The test formulation was applied to one side, while the other side served as control. The animals were observed for 24 hours for any signs of irritation such as redness, swelling, or changes in skin morphology. Absence of irritation confirms the safety of the formulation for topical use²⁸.

Table 1: Composition of different formulation of Mefenamic Acid Emulgel

Ingredients	Formulation Code					
	F1	F2	F3	F4	F5	F6
Mefenamic acid	1gm	1gm	1gm	1gm	1gm	1gm
Sodium Alginate	1%	1.5%	2%	-	-	-
Sodium Carboxymethyl Cellulose	-	-	-	1%	1.5%	2%
Light liquid Paraffin	3ml	3ml	3ml	3ml	3ml	3ml
Tween 80	1.5ml	1.5ml	1.5ml	1.5ml	1.5ml	1.5ml
Span 80	1.5ml	1.5ml	1.5ml	1.5ml	1.5ml	1.5ml
Propylene Glycol	2ml	2ml	2ml	2ml	2ml	2ml
Ethanol	2ml	2ml	2ml	2ml	2ml	2ml
Propyl paraben	0.5gm	0.5gm	0.5gm	0.5gm	0.5gm	0.5gm
Mentha oil	1ml	1ml	1ml	1ml	1ml	1ml
Water	9.5ml	9.5ml	9.5ml	9.5ml	9.5ml	9.5ml

Table 2: Preformulation studies of Mefenamic acid pure drug

Studies	Melting point*(°C)	Identification* (UV) λ_{max}
		Phosphate buffer pH 7.4
Result	231	285
Reported	230-231	285

*Average of three determinations

Table 3: Solubility studies of Mefenamic acid

Solubility ($\mu\text{g/ml}$) *		
Water + Ethanol	PEG 400	pH 7.4
14.8 \pm 0.23	11.5 \pm 0.12	80 \pm 0.10

*Average of three determinations

Table 4: Percent yield of prepared Mefenamic Acid Emulgel

Percentage yield of prepared Emulgel					
F1 (1% Sodium Alginate)	F2 (1.5% Sodium Alginate)	F3 (2% Sodium Alginate)	F4 (1% Sodium Carboxy Methyl Cellulose)	F5 (1.5% Sodium Carboxy Methyl Cellulose)	F6 (2% Sodium Carboxy Methyl Cellulose)
87 ± 0.26	89 ± 0.23	95 ± 0.12	88 ± 0.12	87.8 ± 0.14	90 ± 0.12

*Average of three determinations

Table 5: Physical parameters of Mefenamic acid Emulgel

Sl no	Formulations	pH	Spreadability	Homogeneity
1	F1	5.71 ± 0.18	3.9 ± 0.12	Yes
2	F2	5.8 ± 0.23	4.1 ± 0.19	Yes
3	F3	6.71 ± 0.20	4.4 ± 0.20	Yes
4	F4	6.5 ± 0.29	4 ± 0.11	Yes
5	F5	6.79 ± 0.31	4.3 ± 0.26	Yes
6	F6	6.82 ± 0.28	4.7 ± 0.23	Yes

Table 6: Physical parameters of Mefenamic acid Emulgel

Sl no	Grittiness	Phase separation	Washability
1	No	No	Washable
2	No	No	Washable
3	No	No	Washable
4	No	No	Washable
5	No	No	Washable
6	No	No	Washable

Table 7: Drug content of Mefenamic acid Emulgel

Sl No	Formulation Code	Drug content (mg)*
1	F1	86.88 ± 0.19
2	F2	88 ± 0.21
3	F3	92 ± 0.25
4	F4	87.9 ± 0.31
5	F5	89.78 ± 0.30
6	F6	90 ± 0.23

*Average of three determinations

Fig.1: FTIR Spectra of pure drug Mefenamic acid

Fig. 2: FTIR spectra of Sodium alginate

Fig. 3: FTIR spectra of Mefenamic acid emulgel Formulations-F3

Fig. 4: Comparative in-vitro release profile of Mefenamic acid Emulgel containing sodium alginate – F1, F2 & F3

Fig 5: Comparative in-vitro release profile of Mefenamic acid Emulgel containing Sodium carboxy methyl cellulose – F4, F5 & F6

Fig. 6: Comparative in-vitro release profile of Mefenamic acid Emulgel F3 (2% Sodium alginate) & F6 (2% Sodium carboxy methyl cellulose)

Table 8: In-vitro release profile of Mefenamic acid Emulgel F1-F6

Time (Min)	Cumulative percentage drug released*					
	F1	F2	F3	F4	F5	F6
0	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000
10	7.470	4.347	4.168	4.168	7.024	7.649
20	15.577	6.086	6.173	6.441	8.701	12.901
30	18.052	13.375	10.161	9.986	11.643	17.581
40	19.926	15.114	14.367	11.959	15.238	19.272
50	21.728	18.922	16.562	17.252	18.869	25.619

60	25.509	30.620	18.509	20.545	22.177	32.027
90	35.127	37.971	32.075	26.190	32.834	37.605
120	41.982	44.589	36.048	28.854	36.545	44.306
150	50.956	47.164	55.408	35.648	38.506	47.501
180	56.356	49.137	62.463	38.491	44.141	52.776
210	61.358	53.444	66.461	46.536	49.116	57.921
240	64.710	55.916	72.990	50.194	54.582	65.789
270	66.929	69.295	76.902	57.634	60.812	70.161
300	71.842	74.950	84.326	65.767	66.653	76.891
330	78.404	81.368	90.567	71.567	74.152	85.288
360	92.521	85.255	94.186	75.634	81.721	88.049
390	95.617	96.849	99.528	80.448	86.503	95.293

Table 9: In-vivo studies for Anti-inflammatory activity: Change in rat paw

Time	Control	Standard (Diclofenac 1% Gel)	Test Drug (Mefenamic Acid Emulgel)
0 hour	0.42 ± 0.22	0.46 ± 0.03	0.42 ± 0.02
1 hour	0.41 ± 0.06	0.22 ± 0.05 (52.17)	0.28 ± 0.02 (33.33)
2 hour	0.42 ± 0.04	0.19 ± 0.06 (60.86)	0.22 ± 0.04 (47.61)
3 hour	0.40 ± 0.03	0.16 ± 0.03 (65.21)	0.15 ± 0.04 (64.28)

Values are expressed as mean + S.E.M and % of inhibition of edema was represented in (n=6)

Table 10: In-vivo studies for Analgesic activity Hot Plate Latency Time (sec)

Time	Control	Standard (1% Diclofenac Sodium gel)	Test drug (Mefenamic acid Emulgel)
0 minute	3.26 ± 0.26	3.20 ± 0.26	2.98 ± 0.17
30 minutes	3.42 ± 0.11	8.05 ± 0.24	6.16 ± 0.50
60 minutes	3.75 ± 0.09	10.65 ± 0.30	9.11 ± 0.3
90 minutes	3.52 ± 0.10	10.90 ± 0.14	10.22 ± 0.26
120 minutes	3.24 ± 0.05	11.10 ± 0.28	10.59 ± 0.39

Values are expressed as mean + S.E.M (n=6)

DISCUSSION

The present investigation focused on the development and evaluation of a Mefenamic acid-loaded emulgel as a novel topical drug delivery system aimed at overcoming the limitations associated with oral administration. Mefenamic acid, being a BCS Class II drug, is characterized by high permeability but poor aqueous solubility, which significantly limits its bioavailability when administered orally. Additionally, its oral use is often associated with

gastrointestinal adverse effects such as irritation and ulceration. Therefore, the development of a topical emulgel system was considered a rational and promising approach to enhance localized drug delivery while minimizing systemic side effects²⁹. Preformulation studies played a crucial role in confirming the identity and suitability of the drug for formulation development. The experimentally determined melting point (230°C) was found to be consistent with reported pharmacopoeial values, indicating the purity of the drug sample. Similarly, UV spectrophotometric analysis revealed a λ_{max} at 285 nm, which is in agreement with literature data,

confirming the authenticity of Mefenamic acid and the reliability of the analytical method used. Solubility studies further supported its classification as a poorly water-soluble drug, showing minimal solubility in water but significantly improved solubility in ethanol and phosphate buffer (pH 7.4). This justified the selection of phosphate buffer as the dissolution medium, as it closely mimics physiological conditions and ensures better drug release during in-vitro studies³⁰. The prepared emulgel formulations demonstrated satisfactory physicochemical characteristics. The pH of all formulations ranged between 5.71 ± 0.18 and 6.82 ± 0.28 , which falls within the normal physiological range of skin pH. This indicates that the formulations are unlikely to cause skin irritation and are suitable for topical application. The absence of phase separation and the presence of excellent homogeneity and smooth texture confirmed the physical stability of the emulgel system. Furthermore, the formulations were found to be easily washable and non-greasy, which are desirable attributes for patient acceptability and compliance. Spreadability is an important parameter influencing the ease of application of topical formulations. All emulgels exhibited good spreadability, indicating that they can be uniformly applied over the skin surface with minimal effort. However, it was observed that spreadability decreased with an increase in polymer concentration. This behaviour can be attributed to the increase in viscosity of the gel matrix at higher polymer concentrations, which restricts the flow and spread of the formulation. The drug content analysis revealed values ranging from 87% to 97% with low standard deviation, indicating uniform distribution of the drug throughout the formulation and consistency in the preparation method. The permeability studies demonstrated that the optimized formulation (F3) exhibited a higher permeability coefficient (2.69 ± 0.015 cm/hr) and flux (40.21 mg/cm²/hr), indicating efficient drug permeation. This enhanced permeation can be attributed to the presence of mentha oil, which acts as a natural penetration enhancer by disrupting the lipid bilayers of the stratum corneum and facilitating drug diffusion through the skin layers. FTIR studies confirmed the compatibility of Mefenamic acid with the selected polymers. The characteristic peaks corresponding to functional groups such as N–H stretching, aromatic C–H stretching, and C=O groups

were retained in the optimized formulation (F3), indicating the absence of any significant drug–polymer interaction. This suggests that the drug remained chemically stable within the formulation. In-vitro drug release studies revealed that polymer type and concentration significantly influenced drug release behaviour. The optimized formulation F3 (2% sodium alginate) showed the highest cumulative drug release (99.52% within 390 minutes), demonstrating its superior performance compared to other formulations. The initial slower release observed in F3 may be attributed to the formation of a viscous gel network due to higher polymer concentration, which initially restricts drug diffusion. However, over time, swelling and relaxation of the polymer matrix facilitate drug release through a mechanism commonly described as “solvent drag”. In contrast, formulations containing sodium CMC exhibited comparatively slower drug release, which may be due to differences in swelling behaviour and gel structure. Kinetic analysis of the release data indicated that the drug release followed the Korsmeyer–Peppas model with high correlation coefficients (r^2 values ranging from 0.9949 to 0.9966). The diffusion exponent ($n = 0.9147$ for F3) suggests a non-Fickian or anomalous diffusion mechanism, indicating that drug release is governed by a combination of diffusion and polymer relaxation processes rather than simple diffusion alone³¹. The in-vivo anti-inflammatory study demonstrated that the optimized formulation F3 produced 64.28% inhibition of paw edema, which was comparable to the standard diclofenac gel (65.21%). This indicates that the developed emulgel possesses significant anti-inflammatory efficacy. Similarly, the analgesic activity evaluated using the hot plate method showed an increased latency period for F3 compared to the standard, confirming its effectiveness in pain management. The skin irritation study revealed no signs of redness, inflammation, or irritation over a 24-hour observation period, confirming that the formulation is safe and well tolerated for topical application. Overall, the findings of this study clearly demonstrate that the emulgel system is an effective carrier for the topical delivery of Mefenamic acid. The optimized formulation (F3) not only enhanced drug release and permeation but also exhibited excellent physicochemical properties, stability, and therapeutic efficacy. Thus, emulgel formulation represents a promising alternative to

conventional oral dosage forms for the treatment of localized pain and inflammation.

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